

SOILS ON SLOPES THAT HAVE UNDERGONE ADAPTATION IN RESPONSE TO COMPLEX TOPOGRAPHICAL CONDITIONS

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Abstract. *The article examines the alterations in the soils of the irrigated serozem zone located in the hills of the northern Fergana Valley, driven by anthropogenic factors. Prolonged irrigation of these soils has led to increased density in the plow layer, the onset of irrigation-related erosion, and a marked reduction in humus and nutrient levels. Humus content has decreased to 0.55–1.25% in the plow layer of typical irrigated serozem soils, 0.6–0.95% in pale serozem soils, and 0.4–1.25% in serozem-meadow soils, with values around 1.04–1.30% for the latter. These figures fall below the accepted standards, reflecting a low to moderate supply of essential nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium (NPK), which, in turn, has triggered soil degradation processes in the irrigated serozem zone.*

Moreover, continuous irrigation has led to the compaction of both the plowed and sub-plowed layers of the hill soils in the irrigated areas. Soil density in the upper layer of typical irrigated serozem soils was recorded at 1.28 g/cm³, with light serozem soils at 1.23 g/cm³. In the lower layers (10–20 cm), the density increased to 1.36–1.37 g/cm³, and in the 30–50 cm layer, it reached even higher concentrations of 1.46–1.47 g/cm³ and 1.51–1.57 g/cm³.

Keywords: *typical serozem, light serozem, meadow, humus, salinity, phosphorus, erosion.*

Introduction. The effective use of irrigated land is one of the most pressing issues in the agricultural sector of our republic. A thorough analysis of soil fertility, through the study of genetic and ameliorative processes occurring within it, is essential to understanding the state of soil health. This analysis will support the development of scientifically based measures to prevent and address emerging issues. According to various sources, land in our republic located at altitudes ranging from 500 to 1200–1500 meters above sea level is classified as part of the hill region. This area includes key parts of Tashkent, Fergana, Andijan, Namangan, Jizzakh, Surkhandarya, and Samarkand regions. Based on geomorphological and hydrological characteristics, the hills are further divided into lower and upper hills. The upper hills comprise a significant portion of our republic, as these lands are adjacent to mountainous regions and feature hilly terrain, with rocky soils and dense shrub and undergrowth vegetation.

Prolonged use of hill lands for irrigated and dry farming has led to a transformation of natural landscapes into anthropogenic ones. Increased human activities—such as inefficient use of land and water resources, neglect of land reclamation, and lack of crop rotation—have contributed to the decline in the fertility of hill soils.

Research location and methods of implementation. It is known that the demand for moisture and nutrients of agricultural crops grown in the hilly zone is met artificially. The common soils in the region consist mainly of newly irrigated and reclaimed soils, and cotton-grain and horticultural crops occupy significant areas, and obtaining high yields from them is the main requirement. The northern part of the Fergana Valley, the basin of the Kosonsoy River and the region of adjacent hills are considered to be irrigated serozem zone soils as a research site. At present, the decrease of humus and nutrients in the hilly soil covers, the rapid development of erosion and karst-suffusion processes, the deterioration of the soil structure and the lack of water-resistant aggregates, the presence of water-soluble salts scattered in the soil profile are the causes of negative processes. Changes related to irrigation and development are related to the relief (exposure) of the territory, degree of slope, water permeability, water-physical properties and other characteristics. Taking into account the relief structure of the hilly zone, the physico-chemical properties of the soil and the presence of an impermeable layer, development based on scientific recommendations, preservation of hills and improvement of modern resource-saving methods of irrigation (drip and rain), improvement of the technical condition of irrigation networks are important tasks. Many researchers have studied the soil cover of the Northern Fergana hills [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. The researchers mainly studied the condition of the soil and the demand for humus and nutrients, research methods published in our republic [6], as well as comparative-geochemical, laboratory-analytical and mathematical-statistical data analysis methods [7;8].

Research results and their discussion. A large part of the natural and anthropogenic systems in the hills is made up of agro-landscapes, which consist of irrigated farming, dry farming lands, pastures and meadows. Agrolandscapes formed by anthropogenic factors are characterized by low tolerance to natural-dynamic changes compared to natural landscapes. Because in these landscapes, under the influence of anthropogenic factors, certain changes occur in the life of living organisms, in the water and heat regime, in the process of soil formation, in the exchange of biogeochemical substances, that is, as a result of a slight disturbance of the natural balance, various negative events (erosion, deflation, secondary salinization, desertification, pollution, degradation of pastures, etc.) leads to development [9].

Irrigated agriculture is composed of meridional branching stream basins in the hills, and is better developed in the lower parts of the hills than in the upper parts. The development of collective agrotechnical and agromeliorative activities and recommendations aimed at studying, analyzing, evaluating, maintaining, restoring and protecting the productivity of the irrigated soil of the hilly zone of the Republic and changes related to irrigation is required. The studied area is related to the hill system not only orographically but also geologically. The slope plains of hill fell to the south and extended to the areas of Syrdarya river valley, creating unique agro-landscapes.

According to the relief and geological structure of Namangan region, it is divided into several geomorphological regions based on altitude and zonation, soil-climatic regions [10]. The research area is divided into four geomorphological regions:

- Hills and pre-hill plains consisting of proluvial-alluvial deposits;
- Proluvial-deluvial, soft soil and mixed gravel-soil sub-mountainous plains;
- Middle, upper, and marginal parts of river reaches consisting of proluvial-alluvial deposits;
- Upper terraces I and II of Syrdarya river consisting of alluvial deposits [10].

The hills and sub-hill plains are located in the Chust-Namangan hill system in the north and are composed of rocks mixed with stony soil, sometimes with loess and bedrock. Due to the fact that the hills are strongly folded and subjected to erosion, the thickness of the soil cover is very low, and in some cases, the parent rocks are exposed. The hills are composed of conglomerates, sands, and marly sands of the Upper Tertiary and Quaternary periods. In the northern part of Fergana Valley, the system of pre-mountainous hills is characterized by a dry climate, low atmospheric precipitation, and the presence of dry riverbeds. Their surface is covered with conglomerates, washed gravels and soils (Surson hills) [11]. Sometimes 0.3-1.0 meters of gravel are covered. The most important condition for the region is the badlands of the hill ranges. To the south, the heights of the hills decrease and alternate with wide sloping plains. The hydrogeological conditions of the soil cover are mainly related to the river water level, volume and the level of their use in irrigation. In the movement of groundwater, the central part of the valley and the region of alluvial plains stretching from east to west and Syrdarya river valley are considered to be the zone of the last stage of groundwater accumulation and formation. In addition, the depth of underground water is closely related to geomorphological differences, it is 5-10 m on the slopes of the hill ranges, and 1.0-2.0 m on the banks of the rivers. Their main source is filtered water from rivers and small irrigation channels that seep into the soil in mountains and hills.

As you move away from the mountains, the groundwater in the remote parts of the river reaches does not remain constant throughout the year, that is, it periodically rises or falls. Groundwater is at its highest point during the summer months (irrigation season) and at its lowest point during the fall, winter, and early spring. Groundwater is fresh and slightly mineralized. It is observed that soil covers are formed by interaction of various geomorphological, lithological, hydrogeological and climatic conditions. To the south, the main part of the irrigated land area is gradually replaced by sub-mountain plains with hills and inter-hill valleys, and then turns into plains. The hills are loess-sandy and tertiary rocks are sometimes mixed with conglomerates, sandstones, and limestones. The fact that the hills are composed of loose sedimentary rocks leads to strong washing and surface deformation under the influence of temporary water flows. Beneath the hills, and sometimes between them, the conical reaches of small rivers and the undulating surfaces connected with them, the river reaches formed on proluvial deposits are formed. All the dry valleys between the hills are covered with alluvial deposits of gravel, fine sand and loam on the terraces of Syrdarya to the south. The southern part is connected with Syrdarya river valley and the ancient alluvial plain [12].

In the hills of Kosonsoy river basin, there are mainly 4 types of soils, which are typical serozem, light serozem, serozem-meadow and meadow soils. Under the influence of natural geographical conditions and anthropogenic factors, typical irrigated serozem, light serozem, serozem-meadow, meadow and swamp-meadow soils were formed [13].

Irrigated typical serozem soils occupy the upper parts of the Chust-Pop hill range systems, the loess submontane slopes of Kurama mountain range, as well as the high reaches of Kosonsoy and Podshoota rivers. As soil-forming rocks, proluvial-deluvial and loessed alluvial-proluvial, in rare cases, it forms small-particle deposits with mixed soil [14].

The density of irrigated typical serozem soils in the study area is 1.28 g/cm³ in 10 cm layer, and 1.23 g/cm³ in light gray soils, and 1.36 g/cm³ and 1.37 g in the lower part of this layer, respectively. 1.46-1.47 and 1.51-1.57 g/cm³ in a layer of 30-50 cm, the density of irrigated typical and light serozem soils is directly related to tillage and moisture.

Typical serozem soils that are irrigated have an agroirrigated layer up to 0.7 cm thick. The soil section is compacted, worked by earthworms, and sometimes there are signs of silting. According to the mechanical composition, the soils fall into the category of dusty, medium and heavy sand. Gravel beds are laid at a depth of 1 m in sub-mountain plains, hills, and in some places of cones [15, 16].

The amount of humus in the plow layer is in the range of 0.55-1.25%, total nitrogen is 0.017-0.112%, total phosphorus is very high 0.081-0.500%. The amount of mobile phosphorus is 4.64-18.57 mg/kg, potassium is from 92 mg/kg to 200 mg/kg, the amount of phosphorus and potassium is very low in soils with a sandy mechanical composition. The absorption capacity of the soil profile varies from 9.09 to 12.49 mg-eq per 100 g of soil.

Calcium dominates in the composition of absorbed bases (54.55-72.55% of the total). In the upper layer of the old irrigated soils, carbonates are 6.19-8.20% (SO₂), evenly distributed towards the lower layers, they are mainly in the form of new formations, carbonate nodules and pseudomycelia, the soils are almost non-saline, sometimes low and medium salinity, the soils are moderately washed away, irrigation erosion is observed more often.

Irrigated pale serozem soils are located on the edges of submontane slope plains, in cones and hills. Soil-forming rocks consist of proluvial and sometimes loess deposits. As a result of long-term use of these soils, the thickness is 0.6-1.0 m. and a thick agro-irrigation layer is formed from it, and the reserve loses its features characteristic of serozem soils. According to the mechanical structure, the soils are mainly medium and heavy sandy, and light sandy soils are rare. 0.5-1.0 m in some places. In the submontane plains, they are sometimes skeletal. Depending on the variety of mechanical tillage of the plow layer and agrotechnical measures, the amount of humus is from 0.60 to 0.95%, towards the bottom of the profile from 0.19 to 0.70%, total nitrogen is 0.018-0.102%, the ratio of carbon to nitrogen is 3, 1-7,3. The amount of total phosphorus fluctuates between 0.123-0.330%, mobile phosphorus is 4.33-20.00 mg/kg, exchangeable potassium - 80-270 mg/kg. The absorption capacity is small - 100 g. 8.49-11.09 mg-eq in soil. Calcium dominates in the composition of absorbed bases (61.28-62.19% of the total). Soils are sometimes weakly plastered, sometimes non-saline, low and moderately saline.

Irrigated serozem-meadow soils, as a result of long-term and intensive irrigation of serozem soils, the level of seepage water rose up to 2-3 m, therefore, serozem soils were formed in the process of gradual transition to serozem-meadow soils [17;18]. This also occurred in typical and light serozem soil regions. Irrigated serozem-meadow soils are generally long-cultivated. They are found in sub-mountain slope plains and river conifers, genetically considered "transitional soils" from serozem soil to meadow soils. Due to the presence of a thick (up to 1.5 m) agro-irrigation layer in the section of these soils, residual signs of serozem soils have disappeared. Humidification occurs as a result of groundwater rising through capillaries from the lower part of the soil profile. In this part of the profile, silting has occurred in the form of greenish-blue and rust spots.

The amount of humus varies from 0.43 to 1.28% in the driving layer of the submountain slopes. Depending on the chemical composition of soil-forming rocks, the amount of total nitrogen of 0.037-0.075%, total phosphorus of 0.280-0.330%, mobile phosphorus of 18.00 mg/kg to 26.00 mg/kg, exchangeable potassium of 200-256 mg/kg is enough. Irrigated serozem-meadow soils are low and moderately supplied with humus and nutrients. The mechanical composition is mainly

medium and heavy sand, sometimes light sand, and in some places it is laid with 0.5-1-2m deep limestone and gravel. Soils are non-saline and sometimes slightly saline.

Irrigated meadow soils are formed in the region of light serozem soils and in the desert zone in conditions where the water level is 1.0-2.5 m. Geomorphologically, it was formed in the upper part of rivers and streams consisting of proluvial deposits and in the lower part of the relief, as well as in the lower and middle part of Kosonsoy river basin consisting of alluvial deposits [19; 20].

Large-scale exploitation of the lands in the submountain plains and cones has led to their level rise due to lack of flow of stormwater. As a result of the change in hydrogeological conditions, it was observed that automorphic soils were first transformed into semi-hydromorphic, then hydromorphic meadow soils. The content of humus in the tillage layer of irrigated meadow soils ranges from 1.04 to 1.30%, mobile phosphorus ranges from 11.47 to 26.00 mg/kg, exchangeable potassium ranges from 132 to 250 mg/kg. The irrigated meadow soils are low and extremely supplied with humus and nutrients. Total nitrogen varies from 0.102 to 0.120% depending on the amount of humus. The ratio of carbon to nitrogen is 5.2-6.3, which means that humus has a low nitrogen reserve. The amount of carbonates in the profile of grassland soils is low (7.92-8.18% SO₂). Soils with a light mechanical composition are found in some soil divisions with heavy and medium sandy soils. In addition to non-saline soils, in rare cases medium salinity soils are also found.

Irrigated swamp-meadow soils are found in the marginal areas of river cones and I-II overland terraces. Groundwaters are located at a depth of 0.5-1 m. The mechanical composition of these soils is heavy and medium-sandy, and the section is mainly layered. In some cases, soils on river terraces are 0.5-1.0 m. covered with gravel. Strong siltation of soils starts from the subsoil layer.

Conclusion. The soils studied in the hilly zone exhibited several key characteristics: the presence of leached areas, varying degrees of salinity, low levels of humus and nutrients, and a stone-gravel layer. There was also notable mixing of soil from the surface layers. Overall, it was observed that after irrigation, the soils in this region were primarily characterized by a medium to light loam texture, with some areas showing heavy loam and loam mechanical composition.

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